

The impact of the Self- Assessment and Peer-Assessment on an integrated project

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Abstract

"Peer assessment" and "self-assessment" are both active evaluation methods used in a C++ Object-Oriented Programming integrated project, a module taught to second year computer science students at ESPRIT - School of Engineering. These approaches are used to evaluate projects in which work is divided into phases, each phase is followed by a regulatory validation. We opted for peer and self-assessment methods in order to calculate the continuous monitoring average of this module.

In this paper, we will discuss the implementation of these approaches, their impacts on the learner and some recommendations to improve limitations and have better results in the future.

Keywords: Peer Assessment, Moodle Workshop, Object-Oriented Programming C++, Self-Assessment, Instructor Assessment, Teamwork, Project, Evaluation methods, Engineering Education, Active Learning, Student assessment

1 Introduction

For several years now, many courses and integrated projects have been taught using an active learning approach at ESPRIT namely the module "Object-Oriented Programming C++ Project" (OOP C++Project). The latter consists in a multidisciplinary project where the workload is divided into different sprints with regular control via regulatory validations. It aims at second year common core of IT engineering students. Since the academic year 2019/2020, we have begun to use self and peer-assessment as formative assessment of the project instead of instructor-assessment, in the aim of making this module more active. The final score was included as 30% of the continuous monitoring average.

The students who participated in this study are familiar with active learning approaches such as Project-Based Learning (Alaya, Chemek, Khodjet El Khil, Ben Aissa, & Marzouk, 2016), Problem-Based Learning (Alaya, Khodjet El Khil, & Bettaib, 2015), flipped classroom (Khodjet El Khil, Alaya, & Bettaib, 2016) and Team-Based Learning (Louati, Bettaib, & Derbel, 2014) in their first year.

As a first experience with active methods of assessment in an integrated project, the class was divided into six groups based on a random draw. Teachers of this module chose three active pursuits which are evaluated by different forms of active assessment. The first activity was evaluated by a self-assessment method, the second and the third we opted for peer-assessment. During the first part of the semester, students followed a continuous formative assessment to validate their projects.

Assessment refers to "any methods used to better understand the current knowledge that a student possesses" (Collins & O'Brien, 2003, p.29). Teachers' assessment as the sole assessment tradition in classes is no longer valid nowadays (Leung, 2007)

Various innovations in assessment procedures have been carried out, where the attention to summative assessment has shifted to formative assessment. These innovations involve thinking of alternatives that require questioning the learning process and using learning assessment activities together rather than regular testing methods. Therefore, to overcome the inherent limitations of teachers' assessment, alternative assessment, such as self-assessment and peer assessment, gained momentum in the field of education (Hargreaves, Earl, & Schmidt, 2001).

Self-assessment is conceptualized as “procedures by which the learners themselves evaluate their skills and knowledge” (Bailey, 1998, p. 227). The main merit attributed to self-assessment is that it encourages students to be more actively engaged in the educational process. They are required to reflect on their own performances and encouraged to take greater responsibility in setting goals and making decisions about their own learning (Hughes, & Mylonas, 2002). According to Boud (1995), self-assessment is the technique by which students judge and give feedback on their own performance, which is aimed at improving students' active participation in classroom activities. Boud and Lablin (1983 as cited in Boud 1989) categorized self-assessment as one of the most important processes that can be implemented in undergraduate education because of its potential to develop students' ability to accurately evaluate their own performances and to monitor their own learning.

Peer-assessment is also defined as “an arrangement for peers to consider the level, value, worth, quality or successfulness of the products or outcomes of learning of similar status” (Smith, Swanson, & Elliot, 2000, p. 150). Freeman (1995) highlighted the efficacy of peer-assessment to compensate for weaknesses in many assessment practices that usually fail to foster the development of independent, reflective, critical learners. Similarly, Cheng and Warren asserted that peer-assessment “...provides learners with an opportunity to take responsibility for analyzing, monitoring and evaluating aspects of both the learning process and product of their peers” (2005, p. 94).

Peer and self-assessment, which enable learners to assess themselves and their peers, can potentially encourage them to take greater roles in their own learning by getting engaged with the assessment criteria and reflect on their own performance and that of their peers. Topping (1998) believes that peer-assessment is an arrangement where individuals consider the amount, level, worth, and quality of success of the products or outcomes of learning of peers of similar status. According to Henner-Stanchina and Holec (1985), self-assessment is a technique with which “learners simultaneously generate and undergo the evaluation procedure”. Students' assess their peers' performance and work based on their own evaluation criteria under consideration of their learning objectives and expectations.

Overall, considering the results of the above empirical studies and the significance of both peer- and self-assessment, this study investigated the effectiveness of the implementation of self-peer-assessment in an integrated project. In the next paragraph we will describe the module then our approach and how it was implemented. At the end, we will analyze the results and finish with a conclusion.

2 Description of the module

It is a six-credit module which consists of an integrated project entitled Object-Oriented Programming C++ Project (OOP C++ Project). It is taught during the first semester of each academic year. The former is extended for 14 weeks, and 3 hours of face-to-face coaching per week. This module is intended for second year common core IT students whose number is approximately 270 divided into 9 cohorts.

The project integrated four disciplines; Object-Oriented Programming C++, Oracle Database, Unified Modeling Language Diagram and Arduino. The purpose of this project is to develop all the necessary skills to come up with a real prototype of a desktop application. Students are required to implement a desktop application in order to meet the requirements of their real client.

Teachers prepare a Moodle space related to the project where learners can find all the necessary tools and resources in order to follow up with their courses. Teachers upload assignments for students to complete and add a discussion forum for further interaction in addition to other useful links.

3 Description of the approach

In this paragraph, we will provide a thorough description of the strategy we use to implement self and peer - assessment procedures.

The first step in the implementation of the integrated project is to divide into six groups based on a random draw. Each group is composed by five or six students. As teachers, we provide three activities as homework which are evaluated with an active assessment. The first activity consists in each group choosing a client and

suggesting an application that meets their needs. This is an individual task, during which each member of each group is required to write a version of the specifications following a meeting with the client and to describe the intended services. The duration of the activity is one week. During the following session, each member of each team should assess their work and then compare it with the team members' works. We opted for self-assessment as a method of evaluation. To assess the work, the assessor has to respect a detailed grid which is already prepared by the tutor and then justify each point in feedback.

Many teachers, parents, and students believe that if students have a chance to mark their own work, they will take advantage and give themselves higher scores regardless of the quality of their performance. We have found that students may do this if left on their own. But, when students are trained to systematically use self-evaluation procedures, their judgment becomes more reliable. Contrary to the beliefs of many students, parents, and teachers, students' propensity to inflate grades decreases when teachers share assessment responsibility and control (Ross, et al., 2000). When students participate in the identification of the criteria that will be used to evaluate in-class production and use those criteria to assess their work, they get a better understanding of what is required. The result is the gap between their assessment and the teacher's role is reduced. And, by focusing on evidence, discrepancies between teacher and self-evaluation can be negotiated in a productive way (Carol Rolheiser and John A. Ross, 2013). For this reason, tutors should explain to the students the process of self-assessment, introduce some examples, prepare a grid with detailed evaluation criteria and follow this process in the project session. To improve this skill each team, at the end of this activity, should finalize the project specifications based on the work of each member.

The second activity should be done in groups. Each group is divided into two subgroups. Each subgroup prepares a draft of analysis and design of the application based on the final document of specifications already prepared by the group at the end of the first activity. The duration of the activity is two weeks. This activity consists in a workshop on Moodle Platform. Students should stick to a submission deadline. For the work evaluation, we opted for peer assessment between subgroups of each group. A grid with detailed evaluation criteria was prepared. Assessors and assessees should be part of the same group.

The third activity is also based on teamwork. Each team is required to prepare a prototype of their executable desktop application and submit it on Moodle. The duration of the activity is three weeks. We also plan this activity on Moodle platform as a workshop with a deadline for submission. After the deadline, each group assesses the work of the other groups and gives their feedback. A grid with detailed evaluation criteria is prepared and submitted by the tutors. At the end of this workshop, each team should finalize the application and take notes of their peer-assessor's comments.

According to Bouzidi and Jaillet: « Peer-assessment can be trusted if applied to exams referring to the exact science field and if marked by at least four peers » (Bouzidi & Jaillet, 2009). That's why tutors should interfere to manually verify whether the assigned work submitted by each team is accessible to the other five groups.

For the second and third activities, the deadline to complete the evaluation was three days. After that, tutors verify that assessments are well done and alter scores if necessary. Finally, the results are published to the students.

The score of each activity is included as 10% of the continuous monitoring average. The final continuous monitoring average is 30% of the final score of the integrated project's average.

4 Results

4.1 Method

This study was conducted at the beginning of the second semester of the academic year 2019/2020. Quantitative measures were applied. A total of 270 second year students enrolled in this 6-credit module participated in the study. We asked the students to give us their feedback using a paper survey. The survey was anonymous.

We received 230 responses from 270 registered students which is ~85% of the participation rate. We used Google Sheets to analyze the responses.

4.2 Scholar Results

In Tunisia, learners are evaluated with scores between 0 and 20. To validate a project at ESPRIT, a student has to obtain at least 10 out of 20. The module average is calculated as follows:

Average = 30% Continuous Monitoring (CM) + 70% Final Validation

We apply self and peer assessment to calculate the Continuous Monitoring grade.

We compile some scholar results with final average details in Figure 1 and the continuous Monitoring grade in Figure 2

Figure2: Final Average of the project

Figure2 shows the number of students per interval of their averages in 2019-2020. From this figure we can conclude that about 89% of students validated this project similarly to previous years.

Figure 3: Final Continuous Monitoring Average

Figure 3 shows the number of students per interval of their final continuous monitoring averages in 2019-2020. From this figure we can conclude that about 93% of students validated this part.

Table 1: Results of participation

Legend	Activity 1 (SA)	Activity 2 (PA)	Activity 3 (PA)
Workshop submission on Moodle	80%	78%	83%
Students who did the workshop evaluation	78%	67%	80%
Students who validate the workshop	72%	73%	79%

Table 1 shows that 80% completed the first activity, 78% submitted the second activity and 83% submitted the third activity

Table 1 also shows the number of students who evaluated their peers' submissions. 78% of students completed the self-assessment phase of their workshop, 67% completed the peer-assignment of the second workshop and 80% completed the peer-assignment of the third workshop. It shows also the number of students that validated their workshop (activity 1, 2 and 3) and they obtained at least 10/20. Finally, 72% of students validated the first activity, 73% of students validated the second activity and 79% of students validated the third activity.

In Table 1, We can also see that, compared to activity 1 and 2, the number of students who submitted and peer- assessed activity 3 is bigger. Tutors think that at the end of the semester students are more likely to work harder in order to complete their projects.

We also noticed that the percentage of students who validated their activities using peer-assessment is higher when using than self-assessment. Tutors think that the reason is that students became more familiar with the assessment process and criteria than the first activity which applied self-assessment only.

4.3 Survey Results

The survey included 14 open-ended questions about this experience (experiment). Questions with responses are listed here in four tables Table 2: Self-Assessment (Activity 1), Table 3: Peer Assessment (Activity 2 and 3) and Table 4: Overall Satisfaction.

Table 2: Self-Assessment (Activity 1)

Question	Totally Disagree	Disagree	No opinion	Agree	Fully Agree
The deadline was enough to submit the home work	14,80%	20%	6,20%	25,47%	24,63%
The deadline was enough to evaluate the work	16,35%	17,95%	16,67%	37,5%	9,94%
The evaluation instructions were clear	01,41%	19,88%	21,80%	26,61%	30,30%
The rules and steps of the workshops have been clearly explained by your tutor	10,81%	12,63%	11,20%	25,45%	39,91%
The grid was clearly with detailed evaluation criteria	09,82%	10,01%	5,23%	15,81%	40,87%

According to Table 2, we found out that about 50% are satisfied with the deadline of the first activity and said that it was enough to submit their final work. Only 48% said that the deadline was enough to evaluate the work applying self-assessment, 57% think that the evaluation instructions were clear, 65% said that the rules and steps of the workshops have been clearly explained by their tutor and 57% said that the grid was clearly detailed.

Table 3: Peer Assessment (Activity 2 and 3)

Question	Totally Disagree	Disagree	No opinion	Agree	Fully Agree
The deadline was enough to submit the home work	15,83%	12,71%	20,20%	11,86%	38,47%
The deadline was enough to evaluate the work	16,35%	17,95%	16,67%	9,94%	37,5%
The evaluation instructions were clear	19,56%	19,88%	21,80%	26,61%	9,30%
Course materials provided on Moodle were relevant	33,02%	27,89%	21,16%	12,18%	3,85%
The rules and steps of the workshops have been clearly explained by your tutor	22,76%	11,86%	20,52%	30,77%	11,86%
The grid was clearly with detailed evaluation criteria	07,82%	12,01%	9,23%	11,81%	40,87%

As we can see in Table 3, about 51% are satisfied with the deadline and said that it was enough to submit their final work. Only 48% said that the deadline was enough to evaluate the work applying the peer assessment, 16% are satisfied by the course materials uploaded to Moodle, 43% said that the rules and steps of the workshops have been clearly explained by their tutor and 53% said that the grid was clearly detailed.

We list below some comments extracted from our survey:

“We need more flexibility in terms of deadline “

“More instructors and details about the work required”

“Dispose more clear videos with explanation, more explanations from my tutor”

Since it was our first experience, we can understand the different opinions shared by several students. For the coming year, we planned to work on several points in order to improve this experience. We propose to plan more training sessions to our team of tutors, have some videos on Moodle to explain each phase whether in the self and peer-assessment activities. We should also improve the course materials available on Moodle, explain the steps and rules in the assignments and provide more details about the process.

Table 4: Overall Satisfaction

Questions	Totally Disagree	Disagree	No Opinion	Agree	Fully Agree
The final mark reflects your work done	08,03%	19,20%	5,30%	22,44%	44,70%
The active assessment was a good experience	16,78%	15,65%	9,80%	12,54%	45,23%
Teachers assessment is more reliable	15,67%	51,61%	8,93%	12,45%	11,34%
I feel that I can do better next time	7,38%	2,57%	10,58%	32,06%	45,20%

We can see in Table 4 about 68% are satisfied with their grades and think that it reflects their effort. We can see also that about 58% were satisfied with the experience of active assessment so learning with self and peer assessment was a good experience. 68% don't agree with Teacher-assessment and said that it is less reliable than active assessment. However, less than 10% believe that they cannot do better next time.

We list some comments extracted from our survey:

"Personally, I admired the self-assessment method, it allowed me to learn how to correct my mistakes "

"It is the first time that I feel like a principal actor in the process of my evaluation"

"I think that we must apply the active assessment in all of our courses"

The purpose of using this method is to give the student an opportunity to contribute in the process of their own evaluation.

Thanks to this survey, we detected that self-assessment can encourage students to critically reflect their own learning progress and performance. It enhances their critical-thinking skills mainly when they assess the work of other group members. More feedback can be generated by students compared to one or two teachers. It also helps them become more aware of their weaknesses and strengths. Peer and self-assessment reduce the time and workload of marking for teachers.

On the other hand, we noted that self-assessment can be subjective as students can be unreliable in their grading and may even over-evaluate their own performance. They may also have a tendency to give everyone the same grade, i.e all the groups get goods marks.

For this reason, we decided to offer other unrated activities in order to familiarize students with the evaluation process and control them.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we presented our implementation of active assessment approaches which are self and peer-assessment in our project using the Moodle Platform. The purpose was to ascertain that this approach represents a viable alternative to traditional assessment methods.

The results of the study showed that these approaches have good impacts on grades and a better assimilation of learning outcomes of the module.

While the results are encouraging, we think that some adjustments should be made to improve the whole experience. Improvements include setting up a communication strategy to better explain the process, designing a detailed grid of each part, adding other resources on Moodle and providing several training sessions for students and tutors in order to familiarize them with the assessment criteria.

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